

Akinyemi, FO. **Remote Sensing and Geospatial Methods for Sustainable Land Systems.**
Habilitation Thesis, Faculty of Science, University of Bern

Summary

The research presented in this habilitation thesis reflects recent advances made in remote sensing and geospatial cloud computing technologies. It examines how the changes made to land use and land cover are linked to degrading processes in ecosystems. Land cover refers to the biophysical attributes of the land, whereas land use refers to the human imprint on land as relating to its use. Land use and land cover as well as the human and environmental factors shaping them are collectively referred to as land systems (McConnell 2015). Changes made to land systems, whether by society and/or nature have profound effects on ecosystem functions and processes.

With land system science as the application domain, my research has the goal of advancing the use of integrated satellite remote sensing image data capture and geospatial analytical approaches to investigate land system changes and their impacts such as land degradation. To achieve this goal, it maps and characterises land system changes by quantifying their extent and intensity using mainly remote sensing and field data. These forms the basis for linking the patterns of land system changes to ecosystem processes at the appropriate spatial and temporal scales in different Earth environments. Assessing land system changes involves mapping and quantifying transitions among broad land use types from an initial to a final year (e.g., the forest is converted to cropland between 2002 – 2014. Such a transition is not necessarily permanent over time as any of these three states are possible, i) forest transitions to another use (e.g., cropland); ii) forest remains unchanged; iii) forest transitions to cropland at an earlier period and re-converts back to forest afterwards due to cropland abandonment. A simple analysis of change between two time steps may not capture such intermediate possible states. Thus, assessing the intensity and the direction of the observed changes during multiple time intervals is essential to better understand land system change. Four recurrent themes in my research as presented in this thesis are as follows:

Multidecadal assessment of land system change with remote sensing and GIS

The first part of the thesis examines the dynamics of the land systems in terms of the direction and intensities of observed changes. Cases of land transformation in forested and agricultural mosaic landscapes were examined in different Earth environments. The first case is the central Albertine Rift region in western Rwanda (a biodiversity hotspot in the tropical savanna region — Koppen's Aw — in East Africa). Here, land system changes are mainly due to urbanization processes and agricultural expansion. Subsequent steps were taken to detect and quantify the intensities and direction of land system changes in an urban context using the case of Kigali City (Rwanda's capital). I analyzed the change intensities at three levels (i.e., time interval, category and transition levels). The interval level compared the overall change during the first interval (1981 – 2002) to the overall change during the second time interval (2002 – 2014). The category level describes the variation in gross loss intensity and gross gain intensity among land use categories within each time interval. The transition level describes the variation in the intensity of a particular category transitioning to other categories within each time interval.

Insights derived by examining the direction of the changes during the two time intervals (i.e., 1981 – 2002, 2002 – 2014) include stationary transitions such as settlements expanding into

croplands during both time intervals. I further tested these detailed level analyses of land system change intensities in a follow-up study in Palapye, Botswana (a semi-arid region — Koppen's BSh — in Southern Africa). Results show that land change accelerated from the first time interval (1986 – 2000) to the second time interval (2000 – 2014) as increased urbanization and drought drove land transformation in this semi-arid context. The same stationary transition of settlements expansion into croplands that were identified in the Rwandan case study was found also in the Botswana case study. When a transition is stationary, this means that the same change pattern occurs during all time intervals. Implying that the land system change patterns are stable over time, such identified stationary transitions are useful for understanding the underlying mechanisms of the observed change. Such identified stationary patterns can further support deriving generalizable insights about land system changes across different regions, especially in Africa.

2. Linking Patterns to Processes with Remote Sensing and Ecology

Section two examines the influence of land system change and land degradation on ecosystem outcomes. The aim is to better understand how such changes to land systems exacerbate the vulnerability of coupled human and natural systems. **Capturing the multidimensional features of land system change and linking it to land degradation necessitates the use of a multi-methods approach.** Due to the interdisciplinary context of this research, I combine the use of remote sensing data time-series of vegetation indices with methodologies from Spatial Ecology (e.g., landscape metrics), Soil Science and Soil Microbiology.

Knowledge about how land system change is related to degradation, especially the effects on vegetation and soils, is often lacking, although needed to sustainably manage land-based natural resources. I incorporated remote sensing vegetation indices data with field inventory data of tree species diversity and abundance to decipher how tree species composition is linked to vegetation degradation in nine agro-pastoral locations in Palapye, Botswana. Tree species richness, diversity and rainfall explained 49% of the variance in degradation levels. For example, the non-occurrence of economic trees (e.g., *Sclerocarya birrea*, *Lonchocarpus capassa*) on degraded sites suggests a link between tree species composition and degradation levels in agro-pastoral contexts. Further examination of soil physicochemical properties under three land use regimes reveals that soil bacteria abundance and diversity were influenced by soil properties. Bacterial diversity, known to be a driver of soil ecosystem functions, was mostly influenced by the degree of habitat disturbance from land management practices affecting the soils' physicochemical properties.

3. Understanding Climate and Land Use Change Relations

The third section of this thesis aims at **providing evidence of land use and climate relations.** When changes to land use trigger or exacerbate processes that degrade land-based natural resources, the ability of such lands to respond resiliently to climatic stressors and the negative impacts of human activities decreases (Webb et al. 2017). For example, the spatiotemporal variations of land surface temperature (LST) under the influence of land use were examined in Gaborone, Botswana (2000 – 2018). Increased LST was found during the day and night time over croplands driven by drought. I also was interested in gaining how smallholder farmers perceived drought impacts and changes to rainfall characteristics during the rainy season. This necessitated relating farmer perception data to results from the analysis of climate data. In instances where farmers perceived reduced rainfall amounts, climate time series analysis instead showed high variability in rainfall. For example, crop farmers adapt to climatic changes they perceive by

planting multiple drought resistant crops on the same field. Planting multiple crops is a safeguard as drought impacts vary by crops. Farmers are supported by government programmes providing them with drought resistant crops.

4. Advancing Approaches for Operationalizing and Validating the Land Degradation Neutrality — SDG 15.3.1 indicator

Section four presents **my research contributions to developing advanced remote sensing and geospatial analytical metrics for assessing and modelling LDN**. My research aims at contributing to the understanding of how changing land systems exacerbate the vulnerability of ecosystems to land degradation. Although such knowledge is crucial to support transformation towards land use sustainability, often the required method and/or data are lacking. For example, in the absence of local and national datasets, the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD) recommended the use of global-level datasets for national-level assessment of Land Degradation Neutrality (LDN) and its corresponding Sustainable Development Goal 15 indicator — SDG 15.3.1 — the proportion of degraded land to the total land area. Consequently, countries report estimated degradation levels with low confidence as these estimates are rarely field verified and global datasets do not properly capture local realities. The limitations of using global datasets at local levels are becoming obvious as global datasets are unsuitable for localized policy-making and for investigating potential sustainable land management measures which are often contextual. With only seven years until 2030, practical and technical solutions to monitor progress on the SDGs are urgently needed.

Building on the recent advances in geospatial analytical tools for analyzing and modelling spatial big data, especially remotely sensed image data, **my research contributions to methodological advancement for assessing and modelling land use and land degradation include** i) the development of approaches to create local and national level metrics (e.g., annual land cover and land productivity dynamics) of improved spatial and temporal resolutions; ii) the design and development of spatial data models and databases with local level field data of 17 physical, biological, and chemical land degradation indicators, including physicochemical soil properties. These local-level datasets were used for the field verification of the LDN estimates derived from remote sensing. All metrics and indicators which were implemented for Botswana and Switzerland are currently undergoing further testing in other countries such as Nigeria. Thus, my research has made key contributions to the analysis of spatially explicit biophysical and social land degradation indicators for advancing the sustainable use of land resources.

5. Current and Future Research Outlook

For my EU-funded Marie Curie project — LucFRes (2022-2024), I am characterizing smallholder farming systems (SFSs) to better understand how changing land systems are undermining their resilience. I integrate both quantitative (e.g., remote sensing time series data) and qualitative data (e.g., farmers' perception and social surveys) to analyze the resilience of SFSs. My future research will entail developing scenarios of land use futures for designing development pathways in smallholder contexts experiencing intense land transformation. Potential trade-offs will be considered and synergies between land uses will be promoted where there are competing land demands. Also, as climatic and development factors drive changes to land systems, I plan to examine how persistent agricultural areas in Africa and Europe are likely to change in the future.